

Roundpics Based on Process Approach to Improve Students' Achievement in Writing

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ABSTRACT: The objectives of this study are; 1) to find out the significant difference of student's writing achievement between those who were taught through the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique, and 2) to find out the difference of students' perceptions between those techniques. A quantitative and qualitative study in the form of control group pretest-posttest design was conducted which involved two classes; each class consisted of 21 students of MTSS Darul Huffazh, Pesawaran, Indonesia. The data were analyzed through the independent t-test. The results show that the students' writing achievement in the experimental class increased from 38.76 to 68.95 and there is a significant difference with the sig. (2 tailed) of $0.00 < 0.05$. The result in the control class also increased from 37.81 to 49.05 and there is a significant difference with the sig. (2 tailed) of $0.00 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the result of the significance value of the experimental class and the control class is $0.00 < \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that there is a significant difference in students' writing achievement between the students who were taught using the modified roundtable technique with pictures and the original roundtable technique. Meanwhile, for the second research question, the researcher used a questionnaire measured using a five-range Likert scale and analyzed through the independent t-test. The results show that there was a significant difference in the students' perceptions. The positive responses of students toward the modified roundtable technique with pictures are 74.28% and 70.95% toward the original roundtable technique. The findings suggest that language teachers need to provide other media to help students find new information easily. In conclusion, learning using modifying roundtable technique with pictures is more effective on students' writing achievement than those who were taught through the original roundtable technique.

KEYWORDS: Modified Roundtable Technique, Process Approach, Perception, Picture, Writing Skill.

INTRODUCTION

In this study, the researcher offers teachers to use cooperative learning as an alternative to teaching writing because cooperative learning works in a team. The spirit of competitiveness of individualism may be reduced and lessened by adopting the approach of cooperative learning that provides a supportive learning environment for students in which they can acquire and exchange ideas, information, and knowledge (Mahmoud, 2014). According to Mandal (2009), there are a lot of cooperative learning techniques. They are Jigsaw, Think Pair Share, Three Step Interview, Roundtable, Three Minute Review, Number Heads, etc. From all those techniques, the researcher chooses a Roundtable to teach the writing of the descriptive text. As stated by Barkley (2003) cited in Handayani (2012), one of the best techniques for stimulating ideas and finding a direction for a piece of writing is Roundtable. In Roundtable, each student takes turns responding to a prompt by writing one or two words or phrases.

Kagan (2009) states that the roundtable method is extremely important since students take turns contributing to the group in an oral round-robin form and a written form roundtable. For the roundtable, there is usually one piece of paper and one pen for the team. One student contributes and then passes it to the student on his or her left. The paper or pen goes around the table. If the contributions are oral rather than written, it is called a round-robin. This idea is in line with Handayani (2012) who investigated about roundtable technique to improve students' writing achievement in writing hortatory exposition text in SMAN 1 Ngaglik, Sleman. Some researchers applied cooperative learning techniques mostly for university students and senior high school students. The area that has not been explored well is conducting the techniques in writing descriptive text to teach students of junior high school.

However, the previous studies were still limited in the implementation. Putri et al. (2017) state that in Round Table every student needs to contribute their ideas for the group's task. Some students who have low proficiency in English usually have difficulty in

conducting the roundtable technique because some students experience difficulties and are stuck in writing compared to their other friends who have higher English skills in writing. This causes the roundtable technique to run less effectively because students who are dominant in writing are students who have better English skills than their friends who have low English proficiency. Apart from that, previous studies, namely Fidyati et al. (2016) suggested modifying the roundtable technique to meet students' needs because it is known that not all learning problems can be solved with this technique. Therefore, to overcome the weaknesses of the round table technique, researchers modified the round table technique with media, namely pictures.

Besides, Barkley et al. (2005) as cited in Putri et al. (2017) state that the structure requires all students to post and limits some group members from posting too frequently. That means, in Round Table, all students need to contribute their ideas for the group's task. Fitri et al. (2017) state that the teacher can use the Round Table Technique as one of the various techniques in teaching writing. Not only for writing ability but also because of the effectiveness of the Round Table Technique in creating a better classroom condition where the students were free to deliver their ideas. Then, the limitation is related to the teacher. The teacher must always control and monitor the class while doing the discussion and make sure that all of the students are on a good track. This means that the roundtable technique still has limitations in improving students' writing. In this research, the roundtable is modified based on the process approach where the students share ideas during every stage of writing based on the teacher's direction. To solve the stated obstacle above, it is a good idea to implement a process approach in the roundtable technique. This was done based on Kagan's (2009) study that in cooperative learning if the teacher does not give input or direction, it would be the blind leading the blind. It means that the specific direction modeled by the teacher is important in implementing the roundtable technique. In addition, Alodwan and Ibnian (2014) suggested that the process approach to writing should include several steps, namely; pre-writing, drafting, revising, editing, and publishing. Furthermore, in this present study, the researcher modified the roundtable technique based on the process approach to solve students' problems at each stage of the writing process (pre-writing, drafting, evaluating, and revising) through learning pairs.

Besides technique, to overcome the problems of students who are stuck in writing, it is a good idea to use media. Media can enhance students' writing and encourage them in the teaching and learning process. The picture is one of the media which is provided easily by teachers. It also gives the background knowledge to build their ideas based on the picture they see. Examples of pictures are paintings, sketches, photos, etc.

Furthermore, several studies have examined the use of picture series in the teaching and learning process. In the first previous study done by Kartika et al. (2017), the result of the research showed that the use of pictures can improve the students' writing skills covers (1) students can express their ideas after being stimulated with pictures; (2) students are able to organize their idea in the generic structure of the descriptive text; (3) students are able to use the proper vocabulary based the content of sentence; (4) students had fewer mistake in grammar; (5) students are able to use correct spelling and punctuation. It is shown that there was an improvement in students' writing after being taught with pictures.

Based on the elaborations above, the study aims to investigate a modified roundtable technique through a picture based on the process approach that is effective in improving students' achievement in teaching writing descriptive text. In this case, the researcher combined the roundtable technique and process approach in the learning process through the picture as the media. Roundtable is a technique that asks the students to work in turn in a group, which means it can build good communication among students in the class to share their ideas. Meanwhile, the process approach is an approach that inspires students to understand and plan the sequence and interactions of processes in the system. Therefore, the ideas will be written and organized well. Then, the picture itself is a medium that can attract more students' attention in class, develop students' ideas, and improve students' writing at every stage of writing.

Furthermore, based on the explanation above the researcher conducted research about implementing a process approach in modifying the roundtable technique with the picture in teaching writing. In this case, the researcher modified the roundtable technique and process approach in the learning process with the picture as the media. Nowadays, researchers who modify roundtable techniques and process approaches in teaching writing are still rare. Roundtable is a technique that asks the students to work and discuss in a group, which means it can build good communication among students in the class to share ideas. Meanwhile, the process approach is an approach that inspires students to think systematically and includes several steps, namely pre-writing, drafting,

revising, editing, and publishing. Therefore the ideas will be written and organized well. Then, the picture itself is a medium that can attract more students' attention in class and it also can build their critical thinking in identifying information from pictures. Moreover, the researcher researched a modified roundtable technique with pictures based on the process approach. In this case, the researcher called it the "Roundpics Technique".

Knowing students' perceptions in the learning process is very important because it conducted a roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach. Asking students' perceptions in this research to find out students' points of view about the process approach in the roundtable technique, was also used to measure how far the students could think critically to solve a given problem. Robbins and Judge (2016) say that perception is a process by which we organize and interpret sensory impressions to give meaning to our environment. According to Goldstein (2010), the field of perception is concerned with explaining the operation of the senses, experiences, and behaviors resulting from the stimulation of the senses. In arranging the items for the questionnaire in this research the researcher focused on three indicators, namely: (1) English attitude (student's perspective of the technique), (2) Experiences (how is the practical knowledge of facts about the application of the technique), and (3) Behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to the technique).

Therefore, the researcher conducted a process approach in the roundtable technique with the picture to find out 1) the significant difference in the student's writing achievement after those are taught through the modified roundtable technique with the pictures based on the process approach and original roundtable technique, and 2) the significant difference in students' perceptions between students who were taught through a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on process approach and students who were taught through the original roundtable technique ?

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Writing

One of the important skills that foreign language students need to develop is writing. It is important because not only students but also people can express and elaborate their ideas and information in written form. Regrettably, writing is not as simple as it is because it needs more complex capabilities to generate ideas and organize them coherently. Besides that, writing engages in many recursive processes, some of which necessitate the assistance of experts for the text produced to have any real meaning.

2.2 Roundtable Technique

Based on Barkley et al. (2005) as cited in Putri et al. (2017), roundtable is a technique where the students take a turn responding to a prompt by writing one or two words or phrases before passing the paper along to others who do the same. It is a written version of Round Robin's Brainstorming. It makes understudies dynamic and dependable in their bunch. Besides, each part of the gathering is dependable on the instruction given. Roundtable procedure could be a useful strategy to utilize in a piece of activity. It can be a procedure that makes a difference for understudies to brainstorm their ideas or their contemplations around the subject and review it in a bunch. The roundtable technique was originally designed for teaching writing, but in practice, this technique can be developed to teach all kinds of subjects and skills.

According to Kagan (2009), the steps of the Roundtable Technique are:

1. The teacher provides a task to which there are multiple possible responses and provides think time.
 2. Students take turns passing a paper and pencil or a team project, each writing one answer or contributing.
- Based on the explanation above, the roundtable technique is believed to be able to help students elaborate ideas to write a text. Dealing with that, the researcher modified the roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach to improve students' writing achievement in descriptive text, especially when describing someone.

2.3 Process Approach

The study modified the roundtable technique based on the process approach to help students solve the problems at each stage of the writing process (pre-writing, drafting, evaluating, and revising) (see e.g.e., Richards and Renandya, 2002; Alodwan and Ibnian, 2014; and Rusinovci, 2015).

Crucially, the procedures of a modified roundtable technique based on the process approach can be illustrated as follows in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Modified roundtable technique with pictures based on the process approach.

Further explanation of the table above is as follows:

1. Pre-Writing - Roundtable technique with the picture.

In this stage, the teacher asks the students to divide into several groups, consisting of five to six students in each group, and make a roundtable. The teacher then explains the topic that will be discussed together and the teacher gives a picture to each group. The students observe the picture and write a description of the picture.

Please look at the pictures and write your ideas on the paper!

2. Drafting - Roundtable technique with the picture.

In this stage, the teacher gives a piece of drafting paper to each group and lets it go around the table followed by the paper and the picture.

Please write the sentence as much as possible based on the list as an option and the picture as a guideline!

3. Revising - Roundtable technique with the picture.

After the drafting, the teacher shows the picture and the student's handwriting on the whiteboard. After that, the teacher gives comments and feedback. Then, the students in each roundtable group were instructed to produce a final text in turn by considering the text structure (generic structure of the descriptive text) based on the previous drafting paper.

Please write the revised text based on the previous drafting paper and the picture as a guideline. You can work together in your group, the friend next to you as a mentor!

4. Editing - Roundtable technique with the picture.

Typically the altering organizes in which the individuals of the bunches take turns rectifying their last composing by, to begin with erasing the erroneous ones and taking the duty to type in the proper ones. In this arrangement, the understudies still can look at their pictures.

Please discuss and re-check your work together!

5. Sharing and Publishing - Roundtable technique with the picture.

After executing the four stages over, the teacher asks the students to write individually based on the picture.

Please submit your final pieces of writing!

In conclusion, the researcher in this research did the five steps of the writing process as stated above.

2.4 Modified Roundtable Technique with Pictures Based on Process Approach

This research modified the theories from Kagan (2009) about the roundtable technique to create clear steps for students to develop students' responsibilities. On the other hand, to improve students' ideas, this technique was modified with a picture based on the process approach. The process approach is a method of thinking applied to understand and plan the sequence and interactions of processes in the system.

Furthermore, in this present study, the researcher modified the roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach to solve students' problems at each stage of the writing process (pre-writing, drafting, evaluating, and revising) through learning pairs.

The differences between Kagan's roundtable techniques with the implementation of a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach are as follows:

Table 2.1. The Differences between Kagan's Roundtable Technique and with Roundtable Technique with Pictures Based on Process Approach.

Kagan's Roundtable Technique	Modified Roundtable Technique through Pictures
1. Pre-Writing The teacher assigns a topic or question and ideas think time.	1. Pre-Writing The teacher assigns a topic or question and provides think time through the roundtable technique and picture.
2. Drafting All students respond, in turn, by writing, drawing, or building something with manipulative.	2. Drafting In the roundtable, all students respond, in turn, to write something based on the picture.
3. Revising The teacher signals time or students place thumbs up when done with the problem.	3. Revising Students revise their work in the roundtable technique based on the teacher feedback and picture as a guideline.
4. Editing Students pass papers or projects one person clockwise.	4. Editing Students pass around the paper and edit their work one by one based on the picture.
5. Sharing and Publishing Students continue, adding to what was already completed.	5. Sharing and Publishing The students share their work based on the picture.

Based on the table above, it can be seen that there are differences between Kagan's roundtable technique and the implementation of the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach. Furthermore, the researcher believes that it helps students and teachers active in the learning process and asks students to contribute actively in sharing their ideas to create a good writing text by working in a group.

2.5 A Set of Steps of Teaching Writing through Modified Roundtable Technique with Pictures Based on Process Approach

Here is the explanation of the procedures for teaching writing through the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach:

1. Students are separated into several groups of five to six with a chosen leader and a given theme for each group. The teacher at that point clarifies the definition; generic structure, language features, cases, and models how to compose certain content accurately. One pencil, eraser, and four worksheet papers are dispersed to each bunch. The teacher then describes the stages and rules for collaborative work in the roundtable group. Those procedures continue with group brainstorming for the roundtable pre-writing.
2. The teacher gives a to each group. Each group observes the picture and imagines the description of the picture. The first student writes his idea in words or phrases based on the picture then passes the paper to the next student on the left. The rest of the members continue contributing their ideas to the paper. In this session, the teacher sets the time limit for each member. Each member can write more than one idea or one description on the paper, but they must be different from the previous ones.
3. The next procedure is drafting. In the drafting stage, the first writer tries on to capture the ideas and descriptions on the

paper. The teacher gives a piece of drafting paper to each group and lets it go around the table followed by the paper and the picture. At this stage, students try to produce sentences as much as possible based on the list as an option and the picture as a guideline. The first student produces a sentence or more on the first item on the list by considering the picture. After that, the drafting paper is given to the next student. The next student reads aloud the first student's writing and continues to write sentences on the next item on the list. This process goes for three rounds.

4. After the drafting, it is a revising stage. At this stage, the teacher gives the comments. The writing is revised and developed many times by the teacher. The teacher shows the picture and the student's handwriting on the whiteboard. The teacher gives comments and feedback. Then, the students in each roundtable group were instructed to produce a final text in turn by considering the text structure (generic structure of the descriptive text) based on the previous drafting paper. Every student only writes one sentence. At first, a student writes the first sentence based on the previous drafting paper, and the student on his/her left stands as the mentor. After the paper is passed on, the next student rechecks and revises the first student's writing before writing the next sentence. This process continues for three rounds. If there is one student who cannot express the ideas to write, s/he can write anything even just a single word. The other group members then complete the sentences created by their friends. Once the revision is completed, the students work together in groups to correct the grammar, spelling, and punctuation errors in their work. This is the editing stage in which the members of the groups take turns correcting their final writing by first deleting the incorrect ones and writing the correct ones. In this stage, the students still can look at their pictures.

5. After completing the four stages, students write individually based on the picture.

In conclusion, the researcher believes that modification can improve students' writing in the learning process and make students contribute actively in sharing their ideas to create a good writing text by working in a group.

2.6 Perception

Perception is defined in various ways by different experts. According to Robbins and Judge (2016), perception is a process through which we organize and interpret sensory impressions in order to assign meaning to our surroundings. Zaiturrahmi et al. (2021) also state that perspective is defined as the way of thinking about something or the point of view toward something. According to Goldstein (2010), the field of perception is concerned with explaining the operation of the senses, experiences, and behaviors resulting from the stimulation of the senses. The senses are vision, hearing, the cutaneous senses (touch, pain, tickle, itch), chemical senses (taste, smell, flavor), proprioception and kinesthesia (awareness of body positions and limb position and motion), and the vestibular sense (balance). Based on Goldstein (2010), the researcher focused on three indicators, namely: (1) English attitude (student's perspective on Modified Roundtable Technique), (2) Experiences (how is the practical knowledge of facts about the application of the technique), and (3) Behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to English learning. The questionnaire consists of 10 items with 3 to 4 items in each indicator.

In brief, perception is the recognition and interpretation of sensory information. Perception also encompasses how we react to information. We can think of perception as a process in which we take in sensory information from our surroundings and use that information to interact with them. Perception enables us to take sensory information and transform it into something meaningful.

METHODS

3.1 Design

This study applied a pretest-and-posttest design. For the first research question, the researcher used an experimental design to see students' writing achievement between those who were taught through the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique. Meanwhile, for the second research question, the researcher used the five-range Likert scale and descriptive analysis in the form of a questionnaire to find out students' perceptions after being taught using the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique. In addition, a pretest-and-posttest design was used in this research because, in the experimental group, the students were taught by implementing the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach, and in the control group the students were taught through the original roundtable technique. According to Setiyadi (2006), the research design can be illustrated as follows :

K1	T1	X	T2
K2	T1	O	T2

In which,

K1 : Group 1 (Experimental Group)

K2 : Group 2 (Control Group)

T1 : Pretest

T2 : Posttest

X : Treatment using a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach

O : Treatment using the original roundtable technique

The researcher conducted this research in five meetings. The first meeting was a pretest, the second, third, and fourth, meetings were treatments and the fifth meeting was a post-test and questionnaire.

3.2 Variables

In this research, there are four variables:

1. Students' writing achievement as dependent variable (Y).
2. Modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach as an independent variable (X).
3. Original roundtable technique as an independent variable (X).
4. Student's perceptions as an dependent variable (Y).

It can be stated that in this research there are two independent variables and two dependent variables.

3.3 Data Source

This research was conducted on seventh-grade students during the first semester of the MTSS Darul Huffazh, Pesawaran. The sample in this study was gained by using purposive sampling based on the English teacher's recommendation. It used two classes in single-gender (male); the first class was VII B for the experimental class which consisted of 21 students and the second class was VII C for the control class which consisted of 21 students. The students in the first class were taught using the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach as an independent variable and the students in the second class were taught using the original roundtable technique.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

The procedures of the research are as follows:

1. Determining the population and sample

The researcher chose seventh-grade students of MTSS Darul Huffazh as the population of this research. The researcher took two classes as the sample of the research.

2. Deciding the materials being taught and tested

The material was based on the 2013 Curriculum for seventh-grade students in junior high school. The researcher selected some samples of descriptive text from English books and the internet.

3. Designing the instruments of the research

The instruments of this research are a writing test and a questionnaire. The students got the same instruments in both classes.

4. Conducting a pretest

The researcher prepared the topic for the pretest; it is descriptive text. Furthermore, the researcher asked the students to write descriptive text based on the given picture. The time is 40 minutes for this test.

5. Giving treatments

There are two treatments in this research. The first treatment is teaching writing descriptive text through the implementation of a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach for the experimental class. The second treatment was using the original roundtable technique for the control class. The treatments were given three times to both classes, namely the experimental class and the control class. Each treatment was carried out within 80 minutes.

Each treatment was implemented three times, each treatment was conducted in 80 minutes. In the first meeting, the students get a pretest to see students writing achievement before the treatments. In the second, third, and fourth meetings, the researcher conducted a treatment using a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach to writing a descriptive text based on the given picture to describe someone for the experimental class and teaching using the original roundtable technique for the control class. At the last meeting, a written posttest was administered in the class to see students' writing achievement after being taught the given treatments

6. Conducting posttest

To see the enhancement of students' composing capacity, the posttest was conducted within the lesson on another day. The test was in the form of composing. The students were asked to write a descriptive text and it was done in 40 minutes.

7. Distributing Questionnaire.

To find out students' perceptions towards the implementation of the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique, the questionnaire was administered. The students have to answer ten statements.

3.5 Data Analysis

To get the answer to the second research question in this research, the data were analyzed by using some steps below.

1. Scoring all of the tests using inter-rater.
2. Tabulating the result of pretest and posttest.
3. Obtaining the mean of both tests by calculating the result using this formula:

$$Md = \frac{\sum d}{N}$$

Md : mean (average score)

$\sum d$: total students' score

N : number of students (Hatch and Farhady, 1982)

4. Getting the improvement of students' scores to find whether there is a significant difference in students' writing before and after being taught through the methods. To find the data, the researcher used the formula below:

$$I = M2 - M1$$

I : the improvement of students' writing achievement

M1 : the average score of pretest

M2 : the average score of posttest

5. Contrasting the results from experimental and control groups.
6. Composing a discussion regarding the result.
7. Answering the research question by concluding the result of the analysis.

To answer the second research question about students' perception after the students were taught through a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique, the researcher calculated the responses and totaled all points of each student by using a Likert scale. Then, the researcher analyzed the data using descriptive analysis.

Summarizing all of the explanations above, the researcher analyzed the research questions related to the improvement of students' writing achievement after they were taught using a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Teaching and Learning Process

The learning process was carried out in two classes, namely the control class and the experimental class. Both classes were taught with different teaching techniques. The experimental class was taught using the Modified Roundtable Technique. Meanwhile, the control class was taught using the Original Roundtable Technique. To answer the research questions, the researcher conducted treatments, tests (pretest and posttest), and distributed questionnaires. Data from the pre-test and post-test were checked by two raters, the first rater was the researcher, and the English teacher was the second rater. The data from tests and questionnaires were computed to the SPSS 21 before being analyzed.

4.2 Significant Difference in Students’ Writing Achievement in Both Techniques

This section answered the first research question, is there any significant difference in the student’s writing achievement between those who were taught through the modified roundtable technique and those with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique? The teacher conducted the techniques both on experimental and control groups. The modified roundtable technique with pictures was conducted in the experimental group and the original one was conducted in the control group. To find out the answer to the first research question, the teacher conducted pre and post-tests.

Both the control and experimental groups have been given two kinds of writing tests. Each pre-test and post-test were conducted in 40 minutes. The data were analyzed based on five writing aspects from Jacobs et al. (1981), which are content 30%, organization 20%, vocabulary 20%, language use 25%, and mechanics 5%. Two raters checked students’ writing tests. The scores from both raters were inserted and analyzed using the independent sample T-tests. The following tables present the difference between the two groups in each test.

Table 4.1. Pre-test results for the experimental and control groups

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Score_Pre_Experimental	21	34	80	38.76	3.659
Score_Pre_Control	21	32	59	37.81	4.07
Valid N (listwise)	21				

Table 4.1. shows the results of the pre-test run on both the experimental and control groups. This step was important to check the similarity between the two groups. Results indicated that both of the groups are similar. The students in both groups had the same level of entry behavior.

Table 4.2. Post-test results for the experimental and control groups

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Score_Post_Experimental	21	62	80	68.95	5.343
Score_Post_Control	21	41	59	49.05	5.427
Valid N (listwise)	21				

Table 4.18. shows the results for the post-test run on both the experimental and control groups. Results indicated there was a difference between the two groups in post-test scores. To know the significant difference in students' writing in both the experimental and control groups, the teacher computed the data into SPSS 21 using the Independent Sample T-test. The following tables present the results for the two groups in each test that shows the N gain of students' writing.

Table 4.3. The difference between the experimental and control groups

Difference Significant (Independent T-Test)

Group Statistics

		{ 1, Experimental, 2, Control }	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
NGAIN	1		21	68.95	5.343	1.166
	2		21	49.05	5.427	1.184

The table above shows the N gain among the tests in both groups. These values were used to check the t-test for Equality of Means to know the difference in students' writing.

The mean difference value of students’ writing is 19.905. This value showed the difference range of the students' scores average between the control and experimental group. As mentioned above, there was a significant difference found as far as the control group and experimental group results were concerned.

The result of the pretest and post-test test in both control and experimental groups showed that modification of the roundtable technique with pictures can help students increase their ability to write descriptive text. It could be seen that the sig (2-tailed) value of students' writing scores in control and experimental groups which in the amount of 0.00. It means a lower p-value of 0.05. It can be stated that there was a significant difference in students writing who were being taught using the original roundtable technique and the modified one. Hypothesis testing using independent T-test in the level of trust 95% or the same as the value $\alpha = 5\%$ and also used a degree of freedom value. Based on the data above in sig (2-tailed) value (0.05/2; df) was gotten T Table (0.025; 40) = 1. It concluded that the T value (11.978) was higher than the T table (1), which means H_0 is accepted. The results indicated that there was a significant difference in students' writing between the two groups.

This section is elaboration on the first research question which is the aspects of writing affected the most by implementing the modified roundtable technique with picture and original roundtable technique. The raters analyzed students' writing based on five writing aspects. Meanwhile, the researcher input the data to SPSS 21, to get the result of writing aspects affected the most.

4.3 Students' Perception Toward Modified Roundtable Technique with Picture and Original Roundtable Technique

This section answered the second research question, is there any significant difference in students' perception after being taught through the modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and original roundtable technique? To answer the second research question, the teacher administered the questionnaire to students in experimental and control groups. There are 10 items in the questionnaire which should be answered by the students. The questionnaire has 10 statements of the Likert scale type with 5 choices of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree. The teacher got the result from the Likert scale questionnaire adapted from Goldstein (2010), the field of perception is concerned with explaining the operation of the senses, experiences, and behaviors resulting from the stimulation of the senses. The questionnaire consists of 10 items with 3 to 4 items in each indicator. In this research, the researcher focused on three indicators. Items 1 to 3 are about English attitude (student's perspective on Modified Roundtable Technique). Items 4 to 6 are about experiences (how is the practical knowledge of facts about the application of the technique). Items 7 to 10 are about behavior (how is the seriousness of students in responding to English learning).

Table 4.4. The Analysis Questionnaire Items in the Experimental Group

No .	Questionnaire Statements	Frequency of answer					Total
		SA	A	N	D	SD	
1.	I think English is interesting and always want to take this lesson. (<i>Saya berfikir bahasa Inggris itu menarik dan saya selalu ingin mengikuti pelajaran ini</i>).	10 (47.6%)	4 (19%)	3 (14.3%)	4 (19%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
2.	I am very happy to join this English class. (<i>Saya sangat senang mengikuti kelas Bahasa Inggris ini</i>).	8 (38.1%)	9 (42.9%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
3.	I love my teacher as well as the lesson. (<i>Saya menyukai guru saya begitupun pelajarannya</i>).	13 (61.9%)	3 (14.3%)	4 (19%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
4.	I get good experience during the teaching-learning process. (<i>Saya mendapatkan pengalaman yang baik selama proses belajar mengajar</i>).	12 (57.1%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)

5.	The roundtable technique with pictures makes me contribute my ideas to the group work. <i>(Teknik Roundtable dengan gambar membuat saya menyumbangkan ide-ide saya dalam tugas kelompok).</i>	10 (47.6%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	3 (14.3%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
6.	Pictures give me the background knowledge to build my ideas based on the pictures that I have seen. <i>(Gambar memberi saya latar belakang pengetahuan untuk membangun ide-ide saya berdasarkan gambar yang saya lihat).</i>	7 (33.3%)	6 (28.6%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
7.	I always pay attention to the teacher's explanation when the teacher delivers the material. <i>(Saya selalu memperhatikan penjelasan guru ketika penyampaian materi).</i>	11 (52.4%)	4 (19%)	5 (23.8%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
8.	I always follow the instructions given by the teacher. <i>(Saya selalu mengikuti perintah yang diberikan oleh guru)</i>	12 (57.1%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
9.	I am able to compose sentences based on the picture in the form of grammatical correctness. <i>(Saya dapat membuat kalimat berdasarkan gambar dengan susunan kalimat yang benar)</i>	12 (57.1%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
10.	I am encouraged to do my best to create descriptive text based on the picture. <i>(Saya terdorong untuk melakukan yang terbaik untuk membuat teks deskriptif berdasarkan gambar)</i>	12 (57.1%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)

Based on Table 4.5, it can be concluded that the majority of students have a positive attitude towards English and are enthusiastic about their English class. Based on items 1 to 3 about English attitude, it can be concluded that the students also have a strong preference for their teacher and enjoy the lesson. This indicates a favorable outlook on the learning environment and materials. However, further investigation may be needed to understand the reasons for neutrality or disagreement among some students. From the results in items 4 to 6 about experiences (practical knowledge of facts about the application of the technique), it can be concluded that the majority of students had positive experiences during the teaching-learning process, as well as with the use of the roundtable technique and pictures in contributing ideas in group work. However, there is a noticeable percentage of students who were neutral

or disagreed that the pictures gave them the background knowledge to build their ideas. This may indicate a need for further exploration into the effectiveness of using pictures as a tool to develop ideas in the learning process. Moreover, based on the responses in items 7 to 10 about behavior, the majority of students appear to be actively engaged in their English learning. They generally pay attention to the teacher's explanations and follow instructions. Additionally, a significant percentage of students feel encouraged to do their best when creating descriptive texts based on pictures. However, there is a lower percentage of students who feel confident in composing grammatically correct sentences based on pictures, indicating a potential area for improvement or further support in this aspect of learning.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the students in the experimental group generally have a positive attitude toward English and are engaged in the learning process. They also have good practical knowledge and experience with the modified roundtable technique, and they demonstrate seriousness in their behavior toward English learning. Overall, the students seem to be motivated and actively participate in their English language education.

Table 4.5. The Analysis Questionnaire Items in the Control Group

No.	Questionnaire Statements	Frequency of answer					Total
		SA	A	N	D	SD	
1.	I think English is interesting and always want to take this lesson. <i>(Saya berfikir bahasa Inggris itu menarik dan saya selalu ingin mengikuti pelajaran ini).</i>	8 (38.1%)	9 (42.9)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
2.	I am very happy to join this English class. <i>(Saya sangat senang mengikuti kelas Bahasa Inggrisini).</i>	11 (52.9%)	9 (42.9)	0 (0%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
3.	I love my teacher as well as the lesson. <i>(Saya menyukai guru saya begitupun pelajarannya).</i>	8 (38.1%)	9 (42.9)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
4.	I get good experience during the teaching-learning process. <i>(Saya mendapatkan pengalaman yang baik selama proses belajar mengajar).</i>	12 (57.1%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
5.	The roundtable technique makes me contribute my ideas to the group work. <i>(Teknik Roundtable membuat saya menyumbangkan ide-ide saya dalam tugas kelompok).</i>	10 (47.6%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	3 (14.3%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
6.	My background knowledge helps to build my ideas. <i>(Latar belakang pengetahuan saya membantu untuk membangun ide-ide saya).</i>	7 (33.3%)	6 (28.6%)	4 (19%)	4 (19%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)

7.	I always pay attention to the teacher's explanation when delivering the material. <i>(Saya selalu memperhatikan penjelasan guru ketika menyampaikan materi).</i>	11 (52.4%)	4 (19%)	5 (23.8%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
8.	I always follow the instructions given by the teacher. <i>(Saya selalu mengikuti perintah yang diberikan oleh guru)</i>	12 (57.1%)	5 (23.8%)	3 (14.3%)	1 (4.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
9.	I am able to compose sentence in form of grammatical correct. <i>(Saya dapat membuat kalimat dengan susunan kalimat yang benar)</i>	5 (23.8%)	5 (23.8%)	6 (28.6%)	5 (23.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
10.	I am encouraged to do my best to create descriptive text. <i>(Saya terdorong untuk melakukan yang terbaik untuk membuat teks deskriptif)</i>	5 (23.8%)	5 (23.8%)	6 (28.6%)	5 (23.8%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)

In conclusion, the majority of students have a positive attitude towards English and are enthusiastic about their English class. Based on items 1 to 3 about English attitude, the students also have a strong preference for their teacher and enjoy the lesson, indicating a favorable outlook on the learning environment and materials. However, further investigation may be needed to understand the reasons for neutrality or disagreement among some students. Additionally, it can be concluded that in items 4 to 6 about experiences (practical knowledge of facts about the application of the technique), the majority of students had positive experiences during the teaching-learning process, as well as with the use of the roundtable technique and pictures in contributing ideas in group works. Furthermore, based on the responses in items 7 to 10 about behavior, it can be concluded that the majority of students are generally serious and attentive in their English learning. They pay attention to the teacher's explanation, follow instructions, and are encouraged to do their best in creating descriptive texts. However, there is a need for further investigation into the reasons for neutrality or disagreement among some students, particularly in their ability to compose grammatically correct sentences. This suggests that additional support and guidance may be necessary in this area to further enhance the student's English language skills. Overall, the students demonstrate a positive attitude and engagement in their English learning, but some areas may require improvement and support.

The data were computed into SPSS 21 to get the average of students' perception of every item. The teacher distributed the questionnaire to the students in the last meeting after they had been taught writing using the modified roundtable technique with picture and original roundtable technique. The result of the questionnaire showed that most students have a positive perception toward the implementation of both techniques. It is proved by the percentage of students' answers in questionnaire items.

In addition, to analyze the significant difference in students' perceptions in both the experimental and control groups, the teacher computed the data into SPSS 21 using the Independent Sample T-test.

The average difference value of students' perceptions is 0.720. This value showed the difference range of the students' perceptions average between the control and experimental group. As mentioned above, there was a significant difference found as far as the control group and experimental group results were concerned. The perception results in the control and experimental groups show that modification of the roundtable technique with pictures and the original roundtable technique can provide a positive perspective for students in improving their ability to write descriptive text. It could be seen that the sig (2-tailed) value of students' perceptions

in control and experimental groups in the amounts of 0.012 and 0.014. It means a lower p-value of 0.05. It can be stated that there was a significant difference in students' perceptions of who was being taught using the original roundtable technique and the modified one. Hypothesis testing using independent T-test in the level of trust 95% or the same as the value α - 5% and also used a degree of freedom value. It concluded that the T value (2.775) was higher than the T table (1), which means H_{a2} is accepted. The results indicated that there was a significant difference in students' perceptions between the experimental and control group.

This section elaboration on the second research question is there a significant difference in students' perceptions between students who were taught through a modified roundtable technique with a picture based on the process approach and students who were taught through the original roundtable technique? The researcher analyzed students' perceptions based on the questionnaire and input the data to SPSS 21, to get the result of a significant difference in students' perceptions.

4.4 Discussion

This section discussed the result of the research in covering three issues, the significant difference in students' writing achievement after being taught using the modified roundtable technique with a picture and the original one, the aspects of writing affected the most, and students' perception toward both techniques.

4.4.1 Significant Difference in Students' Writing in Both Techniques

This section discussed the difference between students' writing in the modified roundtable technique with pictures and the original roundtable technique. The result of the pretest is used to check whether students' abilities in both groups are homogenous. To find out the difference in students' writing in both groups, the teacher used the data from students' post-tests. After being taught using a modified round table technique with pictures, the students' post-test—writing scores increased significantly compared to the results in the control group. However, a deeper look into the results indicates that the increase in the experimental group's results was mainly affected.

Pretest and posttest scores are used to analyze the difference in students' writing before and after the application of modifying the roundtable technique with pictures. The difference between the pretest and post-test scores showed that the students' mean score on writing post-tests was higher than the pretest. There was an improvement in posttest scores after the students learned using the modified roundtable technique with pictures. The significant results obtained from sig. value in the amount of 0.000 that was lower than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, it reveals that the proposed alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted. It proved that statistically there was a different increase between the two groups from the results of the descriptive writing pre-test and post-test given to both of the groups. Moreover, the result also showed an increase in the control group showing the mean score in the pretest is 37.81. Meanwhile, in the posttest, the score increased up to 49.05. It indicates that the gain score from the pretest to posttest is about 11.24. It can be concluded that there was a difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the control group which learned writing using the original roundtable technique.

On the other hand, the pretest and posttest scores in the experimental group after being taught by using modification of the roundtable technique with pictures are significantly difference. The gain score between the pretest and post-test in the experimental group is about 30.19. It is quite high compared to the gain score in the control group which only reached 11.24. The students' post-test scores increased significantly both in the control group and the experimental group. It might happen because the modified roundtable technique with pictures allows them to develop ideas and makes them want to take part in collaborative learning. As Kagan (2009) states the roundtable technique will achieve some advantages in terms of academic and social points of view, such as assessing prior knowledge, practicing skills, especially writing skills, creating cooperative art, and team building, and participation of all the students. Moreover, pictures can stimulate students' creativity, especially in writing and they can build up the students' motivation in the teaching-learning process and it could help students to represent their handwriting. As Kartika et al. (2017) state the result of the research showed that the use of pictures can improve the students' writing skills that covers, such as students can express their ideas after being stimulated with pictures; students can organize their ideas in generic structure of descriptive text; students are able to use the proper vocabulary based the content of sentence; students had fewer mistake in grammar; also students are able to use correct spelling and punctuation. Indeed, it indicates that modification of the roundtable technique with pictures used in writing descriptive tests could give a significant increase in students' writing achievement. Also, it stated that picture supports building content and vocabulary. This finding supports the previous studies by Barkley (2003) cited in Handayani (2012) that the

implementation of the roundtable technique can be used in teaching English, especially in writing which successfully engages students in stimulating ideas and finding a direction for a piece of writing.

By modifying modification on roundtable technique with pictures, the teacher found that the students could develop their ideas into paragraphs well compared to students in the control group. It can be concluded that there was a significant difference in students' writing after being taught using a modified roundtable technique with pictures. Especially if we compared the students' writing scores in both control and experimental groups, the total gain scores in those groups are different. As we know the control group gained a score of 11.24, different from the experimental group which had 30.19. From that fact, it means that the students who were being taught using a modification of the roundtable technique with the picture had higher scores than students in the original roundtable technique class.

4.4.2 Students' Perception Toward Modified Roundtable Technique with Picture

The result of the questionnaire is used to answer the second research question. From that result, it can be seen that the students have a difference in perception through both techniques, a modified roundtable with a picture and the original one that is used in teaching writing. From 10 items of questions in the questionnaire, students who answered positively in the experimental group reached about 74.28%, compared to the negative response which students gave only 8.58% of whole items in the questionnaire, and the rest about 17.14% belonged to the neutral. It indicates that the students in the experimental group agree that modification of the roundtable technique with pictures can affect their learning process positively. Moreover, in the control group, students who answered positively in the experimental group reached about 70.95%, compared to the negative response that the students gave only 10.95% from whole items in the questionnaire, and the rest about 18.10% belonged to the neutral. It indicates that the students in the control group agree that the roundtable technique can affect their learning process positively. The data results indicate that the students in the different groups have a positive perception of the techniques used in writing. It happens because the students felt enjoyable during the class, they could elaborate their ideas before writing through stages provided in the roundtable technique. Moreover, it is supported by the statement from Flora et al. (2020), that the modified roundtable based on the process approach, can optimally enable the students to cooperatively learn how to write a descriptive text well because the teacher gave them clear instructions on how to do the activity for every stage of the writing process (pre-writing, drafting, revising and editing). In addition, the topic being discussed was also in their interest. During the pre-writing activities, the students got used to listing the words or phrases related to the topic being discussed and consequently, it made them able to write longer text. However, it is also supported by the statement from Parmawati et al. (2021), that the students have positive responses to the implementation of the roundtable technique. In addition, it is also supported by the statement from Mahardika, et al. (2019), that the student's perception toward the implementation of the roundtable technique was positive. The majority of the students agreed that the modified roundtable technique with pictures was an interesting technique that gave benefits to them.

Roundtable technique which is seen as both a cooperative and collaborative learning technique was able to change the teaching and learning activity into learner-centered. All of the students were actively involved during the teaching and learning activity. They have a high motivation to learn. The students understand the material more easily. The learning process is interesting and not boring. They are motivated to achieve good achievement because they feel more valued in expressing opinions when learning provides some stages that aim for students to relate their prior knowledge to their new learning. From all the students' answers to 10 items in the questionnaire, it can be concluded that the students have a positive perception of modification of the roundtable technique with picture and the original one, so most of them agree about this questionnaire items. Nevertheless, some students disagree with the items in the perception questionnaire. The students said that they did not have time to feel sleepy during the class, because they were forced to think and discuss together with their partners to complete the task. From all the results of data analysis, it can be stated that the modification roundtable technique with pictures and the original roundtable technique can have a positive effect on students' writing and also can build students to have a good perception about those techniques in teaching writing.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusion

1. Modified roundtable technique with a picture is effective to use in teaching writing. Students' ability in writing after being taught using the modified roundtable technique with pictures is quite good, it might be caused by the processes provided in the

modified roundtable technique and picture as media. Pictures help students to catch the ideas and trigger students to write something. Modified roundtable technique with pictures gave students a chance to develop their ideas before writing, collect some information based on the picture, and discuss with partners to make their writing better. Picture can be used to transform abstract ideas into realistic ideas. By looking at the picture, the learners become more engaged in the lesson and pictures also facilitate further learning.

2. Students in the experimental and control groups have positive perceptions about learning how to write using the modified roundtable technique with picture and original roundtable technique. It might be caused by the ambience in the class while conducting the techniques. Those techniques make the students feel enjoyable and interested in following the learning processes. The students were given a chance to have some discussions to develop their ideas, they also had good preparation by listing ideas in the pre-activities.

5.2 Suggestions

Considering the conclusions of the research above, the writer would like to propose some suggestions as follows:

1. Suggestions to teachers

English teachers are recommended to apply a modified roundtable technique with pictures in teaching writing to lead students to develop their ideas in written form. The roundtable technique is considered collaborative learning, so the students are also required to be active and contribute to the learning process. Moreover, in the fourth step, teachers can encourage student motivation to be active by ensuring that they don't skip expressing their ideas in English. Additionally, students are allowed to ask for help from group members.

2. Suggestions for further research

Firstly, the samples of the study were limited to junior high school students in the boarding school who are considered to have lower English skills. Therefore, it is recommended that further researchers examine the implementation of a modified roundtable technique with pictures to improve the writing achievement of students at intermediate or advanced levels. It is expected that the modified technique can give good results for students at all levels so that it can help them enhance their writing skills.

Secondly, the researcher took the participants purposively using intact group sampling as the classes have been adjusted by the school where this study took place. Thus, further researchers who want to conduct similar studies are suggested to use random sampling so the result of the study can be generalized to larger populations. In addition, other researchers may conduct the research not only for male students but also for female students, so the researcher can compare whether gender differences can yield different results or not.

After all, those are the conclusions of this study that investigated the use of the modified roundtable technique with pictures. Other researchers may consider the suggestion above in conducting further studies related to the topic. The findings of this research also offer implications that can be implemented by teachers in the teaching and learning process.

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